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Assessment Of Seasonal Variation Of 5g Signal Strength And Signal Speed Over Abuja, North-Central, Nigeria

Abstract: This research work was aimed at determining the seasonal variation of 5G network signal speed and Signal strength over Abuja, North-Central Nigeria. The research involved the measurement of 5G network signal download and upload speeds, the ping and the Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP) in both rainy season and dry season months of 2024, from July 1 to December 31, 2024. The measurements were taken every hour daily from 8:00 am – 6:00 pm in a particular experiment site using *Speedtest* software and *Netmonitor* application installed on a laptop computer and Infinix Android phone with a Simard of a particular network service provider in Nigeria. The results showed that there were variations in the speed of the download and the upload of the 5G network as well as the signal strength in the study area hourly and seasonally. It was concluded from the results that the average 5G signal strength was higher in dry season compared to the signal strength in rainy season, given that the average RSRP values in dry season and rainy season were -107.9 dBm and -110.3 dBm respectively. It was recommended that the effect of some atmospheric components like rainfall, pressure, temperature on the 5G network signal over Abuja be investigated in future works as they may have some influences on 5G signal in addition to the ping as discovered in this work. This study will inform the infrastructural development strategies and resource allocations in Abuja and other areas.

Keywords: *Download, Netmonitor, Ping, upload, speed, Signal strength*

I. INTRODUCTION

In many countries of the world, mobile networks play a strategic infrastructural role for the economy, thus, the increase of the reliance of community members on mobile broadband networks has resulted to significant challenges for network service providers such as provision of high-quality communication services, providing network coverage adequately, as well as customers' satisfaction experience in some areas [1].

In recent years, there was an increased demand of accessing high data rate applications on mobile device from networks which mainly target on providing high peak data rates, high spectral efficiency, improved capacity¹ and coverage, short round trip time, and spectrum flexibility [2].

One of the major telecommunication applications and innovations with rapid development across the world today is Global System for Mobile Communication [3-5], and it has contributed to the growth of different sectors of the economy. Also, according to [1], Mobile data has become an integral part of everyday life, and that mobile broadband is one of the main aims of fifth-generation networks as a result of increased growth in demand for data. This led to need to examine the end-to-end performance of the network, and ensure a better user experience in their work.

The rising use of 2G, 3G, 4G and 5G classes of mobile phones networks was prompted by Nigeria Communication Commission (NCC) directives to the network operators to improve the quality of service they are offering to the subscribers, as the system or technology will allow more subscribers to the network unlike the analogue systems [6-7].

In order to assess the signal strength of the major network providers in Nigeria, [8], performed an experiment by installing an application called Network Cell Info Lite in three INFINIX GSM mobile phones and was used to

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take the measurement of the signal strength on the campus of Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo State, Nigeria, received from the transmitting stations of different mobile networks- MTN, Globacom and Airtel. It was discovered that MTN has the maximum signal strength of - 68.33 dBm mean value, directly followed by Globacom with -80.41 dBm mean value and Airtel with -83.13 dBm mean value. Though, some similar works in the research areas have been done by some researchers, there is no work which discusses the variation of the 5G signal or a comprehensive study of 5G in Abuja. Figure 1 shows the screenshot of the measurement process of 5G signal strength using *Netmonitor* software.

Fig. 1: Screen view of *Netmonitor* software

II. Study location

Abuja, the study area is the Federal Capital Territory on Nigeria. It has the geographical coordinate of latitude 8.25° and 9.20° north of the equator and longitude 6.45° and 7.39° East of the Greenwich meridian. Abuja is bounded by Niger State to the West and North, Kogi state to the south west, Kaduna state to the Northeast, and Nasarawa state to the east and south. The rainy season takes place between April and September, and the dry season between October and December. Abuja, founded in 1976 from parts of Nasarawa State, Kogi State, and Niger State, has the vegetation of guinea forest savanna. It has some high mountains and a few trees and short grasses with an average temperature of 25.7°C and an annual rainfall of about 1200 mm [13 & 14].

III. Materials and method

The research work made use of quantitative research method; to collect primary data which comprises the parameters of the 5G network signal such as the speed of the download, speed of the upload, the ping and the Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP). The data collection was done with a computer software called *Speedtest* and a phone application called *Netmonitor*. *Netmonitor* has the ability to measure the signal strength of 2G, 3G, 4G, and 5G, displaying other information of the network in addition to the signal strength. The *Speedtest* was used to measure the speed of the download, upload and the ping times making use of the Airtel network which has 5G network in Abuja where the study was carried out. The data (download speed, upload speed, ping and RSRP) were measured at the same time on hourly basis from 8:00 am to 6:00 pm daily from July 1, 2024 – December 30, 2024, at a fixed spot in Abuja town on the frequency of 3.5 GHz. The average of the data for all the rainy season months was calculated to have a single hourly data for rainy season, and same done for dry season months (July- September, and October – December, 30, 2024). The representation of the data was done using tables and graphs, displaying the parameters of the 5G network signal, showing their hourly and seasonal variations. Further analysis was carried out using Pearson correlation analysis to examine the relationship or impact of ping on the RSRP.

IV. Results and Discussions

Table 1 shows the data of average 5G network signal for dry season months, (October, 1, 2024 - December 31, 2024). The table shows average hourly values of 5G network signal's speed of download and upload, the ping (round-trip delay) and the signal strength or Reference Signal Receive Power (RSRP) of the 5G network signal. The results shows that there was an hourly variation of the speed of download signal and the average speed of upload signal of the 5G network in the study area. At 8:00 am, the average download speed was 6.88 ms while the speed of upload signal was 12.9 ms. At 9:00 am, the speed of download was 10.50 ms while the speed of upload was 33.4 ms. Also, the average hourly download speed for dry season months from 11:00 am to 6:00 pm were 9.02 ms, 9.77 ms, 5.14 ms, 7.89 ms, 1.05 ms, 3.65 ms, 5.88 ms and 6.80 ms respectively, while the average hourly upload speed from 11:00 am to 6:00 pm are 3.98 ms, 3.27 ms, 2.02 ms, 5.85 ms, 0.48 ms, 0.40 ms, 1.71 ms and 6.0 ms. This shows that the speed of the downloads and uploads changed with time or almost every hour from 8:00 am to 6:00 pm. In the same way, the ping of the 5G signal also varied almost hourly. From 8:00 am to 6:00 pm, the average hourly ping of the 5G network signal in the study area were 116 ms, 39 ms, 98 ms, 481 ms, 114 ms, 151 ms, 42 ms, 146 ms, 187 ms, 329 ms and 234 ms respectively. This shows that the ping of the 5G signal strength of Abuja varied at irregular interval just like the download and upload speed. From 8:00 am to 10:00 am, it was seen that as the ping was increasing, the download and upload speed were increasing. From 8:00 am to 9:00 am, the download speed changed from 6.88 ms to 10.50 ms while the upload speed changed from 12.9 ms to 33.4 ms. From 9:00 am to 10:00 am, the download speed changed from 8.38 ms to 9.02 ms while the upload speed changed from 33.4 ms to 6.35 ms. This occurred when the ping changed from 39 ms to 98 ms. In other words, as the ping decreased from 116 ms to 39 ms, the download speed increased from 6.88 ms to 10.50 ms. Also, the upload speed increased at this point from 12.9 ms to 33.4 ms. Furthermore, as the ping increased from 39 ms to 98 ms, the download speed decreased from 10.50 ms to 8.38 ms. This same scenario is experienced in the upload speed in which the value changed from 33.4 ms to 6.36 ms. Although this is not always the case in all, as some deviations such as one observed between 10 am to 11 am for download which the signal speed increased from 8.38 ms to 9.02 ms even as the ping was increasing from 98 ms to 481 ms which ordinarily would have been the inverse observation, the normal or similar behaviour as seen at the beginning is observed under the upload between this same 10:00 am to 11:00 am. That is, as the ping changed from 98 ms to 481 ms which is an increase, the upload changed or decreased from 6.35 ms to 3.98 ms. From 1:00 pm to 2:00 pm, there was a decrease in the ping from 151 ms to 42 ms, a corresponding change in the download from 5.14 ms to 7.89 ms, and in upload from 2.02 ms to 5.85 ms, both of which are incremental changes. From 2:00 pm to 3:00 pm, the ping values changed from 42 ms to 146 ms which is an increment. The changes in the downloads and uploads occurred in the form of changing from 7.89 ms to 1.05 ms for download, and 5.85 ms to 0.58 ms for the upload. In other words, as the latency or ping increases, the speeds of the downloads and uploads decrease accordingly. As for the variation of the download and the upload speeds, the town experience an increase or a decrease at almost the same time. This is shown in figure 1. The figure also shows that the magnitude of the upload and the download is higher in the morning period from around 8:00 am to 11:00 compared to other values of the average speeds of the either the download or upload at other time of the day. Figure 2 shows the graphical representation of the ping. It can be observed that the ping also changes at various times, but that the level or amount of ping experienced during the day time is higher compared to the ping being experienced by the 4 G strength in the area in the morning and evening periods. This could be one of the reasons why the download speed and the upload speed in the day time were less since much delay or ping occurred in the day time.

Table 1: Data of average 5G network signal for dry season, 2024

Time	Average Download speed (ms)	Average Upload speed (ms)	Average Ping (ms)	Average RSRP (dBm)
8:00	6.88	12.9	116	-111
9:00	10.50	33.4	39	-102
10:00	8.38	6.35	98	-110
11:00	9.02	3.98	481	-113
12:00	9.77	3.27	114	-107
1:00	5.14	2.02	151	-109

2:00	7.89	5.85	42	-110
3:00	1.05	0.48	146	-109
4:00	3.65	0.40	187	-108
5:00	5.88	1.71	329	-105
6:00	6.8	6.0	234	-103

Figure 1: Graphical representation of download and upload speed in Dry season

Figure 2: Graphical representation of ping in Dry season

The variation of the signal strength is shown in figure 3. The average hourly RSRP value of 5G network signal strength has a negative sign, and the higher the negative value, the poorer the signal quality or weaker the signal strength. From the result on the graph as well as on table 1, it can be said that signal strength also underwent hourly variation just like the download and upload speeds as well as the latency. From table 1, the average hourly RSRP values of the 5G network signal strength in Dry season were -111 dBm, -102 dBm, -110 dBm, -113 dBm, -107 dBm, -109 dBm, -110 dBm, -109 dBm, -108 dBm, -105 dBm, -103 dBm. This implies that the signal strength

of the 5G network in the study area over this study period experienced change in values or magnitude hourly too. From the figure 3, it can be observed that the signal strength was lower in the afternoon period (12:00 pm – 4:00 pm) and that an increase in signal strength was observed in the evening period. However, it can be said that the 5G network signal strength in the study area over this study period experienced changes in magnitude almost hourly.

Figure 3: Graphical representation of 5G network signal in Dry season

Table 2 shows the data of average 5G network signal for rainy season (July 1 to September 30, 2024). From the table, it can be observed that the speed at which the download of data or information was done on 5G network in the study area exhibited changes in values or magnitude. This was also observed in the upload signal speed in the area. The result shows that the average hourly speed of the download 5G network signal changed from 7.72 ms to 5.61 ms, 4.42 ms, 0.85 ms, 10.9 ms, 3.49 ms, 3.49 ms, 9.2 ms, etc. from 8:00 am to 1:00 pm. In the same way, the speed of the download within this same time; that is, from 8:00am to 1:00 pm, are 6.34 ms, 5.61 ms, 8.05 ms, 0.83 ms, 2.42 ms, 0.70 ms at 1:00 pm. This implies that both the download and the upload changed in magnitude over time; these changes in the two speeds are at irregular intervals. The ping of the 5G network in rainy season also varied with time or varied hourly. At 8:00 am, the ping was 80 ms; at 9:00 am, the ping was 60 ms, at 10:00 am, the ping was 120 ms, at 11:00 am, the ping was 345 ms. It also shows that the variation of the ping does not depend on time or varied at equal amount but irregularly in nature. As the average download speed changed from 7.72 ms to 5.61 ms from 8:00 am to 9:00 am, the upload changed from 6.34 ms to 5.61 ms, while the ping changed from 80 ms to 60 ms. Also, as the average download speed changed from 5.61 ms to 4.42 ms from 9:00 am to 10:00 am, the upload changed from 5.61 ms to 8.05 ms, and the ping changed from 5.61 ms to 8.05 ms. This means that as the ping is increasing, the speed of the download and the upload is affected negatively. This is seen from 8:00 am to 10:00 am. In the noon, from 1:00 pm to 2:00 pm, the download an upload speeds changed from 3.49 ms to 9.2 ms, and 0.70 ms to 7.09 ms respectively while the ping was observed to have changed from 176 ms to 62 ms respectively. This shows that as the ping decreases, the speed of the download and upload increases even though it was not in all cases as there are some points such as from 2:00 pm to 3:00 pm in which the upload changed from 7.09 ms to 7.70 ms when the ping increased from 62 ms to 102 ms respectively. But irrespective of the nature of the variation with ping, the download speed and the upload speed demonstrate similar manner of change. As seen in figure 4 which is the diagrammatical representation of the speeds of download and upload, it was observed that the two were higher in the morning period but fell at 11:00 am then rose sharply at 12:00 pm and then falling at 1:00 pm then reaching the peak (in the case of upload) at 3:00 pm when it continued to fall slowly until they both reached the minimum at 6:00PM. The variation or trend of change of the pig (figure 5) shows that the ping was low in the morning and higher around the noon time between 11:00 am and 1:00 pm. It was also observed to be lower from around 3:00 pm to 5:00pm when it rose sharply and continued to 6:00 pm. Though the trends of the variation of the ping (figures 3 and 6) are not entirely the same, there are some similarities

in the nature of the change of the ping in rainy season and the dry season especially around 11:00 am and the evening periods of the two seasons.

Table 2: Data of average 5G network signal for Rainy season, 2024

Time	Average Download speed (ms)	Average Upload speed (ms)	Average Ping (ms)	Average RSRP (dBm)
8:00	7.72	6.34	80	-105
9:00	5.61	5.61	60	-111
10:00	4.42	8.05	120	-108
11:00	0.85	0.83	345	-109
12:00	10.9	2.42	344	-111
1:00	3.49	0.70	176	-115
2:00	9.2	7.09	62	-105
3:00	2.92	7.70	102	-108
4:00	6.64	1.13	148	-121
5:00	3.41	0.78	144	-111
6:00	0.51	1.17	400	-109

Figure 4: Graphical representation of download and upload speed in Rainy season

Figure 5: Graphical representation of ping in Rainy season

Figure 6: Graphical representation of the 5G network signal in Rainy season

The variation of the signal strength in dry season is shown in figure 6. From the result on the graph as well as on table 2, it can be said that signal strength also underwent hourly variation just like the download and upload speeds as well as the ping. From table 2, the signal strength was observed to have changed from -105 dBm, -111 dBm, -108 dBm, -111 dBm, -115 dBm, -105 dBm, -105 dBm, -121 dBm, -111 dBm and -109 dBm from 8:00 am to 6:00 pm in that order. At 8:00 am, the 5G network signal strength was -105 dBm, and later decreased to -111 dBm at 9:00 am. It later increased to -108 dBm at 10:00 a, then decreasing at 11:00 am and 12:00 pm with the values as -109 dBm and -111 dBm. In a simple term, while the signal strength was high in the morning, it was low in the noon period but continued to increase slightly from 3:00 pm to 6:00pm. The figure demonstrates that the variation of the 5G network signal strength is not determined by the period (morning, noon or evening) alone as there may be some factors contributing to the changes. However, the signal strength can be said to experience a change hourly throughout the period.

Figure 6: The average signal strength of the 5G network in Abuja for the two seasons

Figure 6 shows the average signal strength of the 5G network in Abuja for the two seasons. While the average signal strength in the first two hours (8:00am and 9:00am) behave in opposite ways, the characteristics of the two seasons signal strength are almost the same in the remaining period. In other words, the average hourly signal strength of the 5G network was lower at 8:00 am and higher at 9:00 am in dry season, it was higher at 8:00am and lower at 9:00am in rainy season. But after this short period, the pattern of variations in the two seasons were almost the same as the trend were somewhat increasing and decreasing mostly in similar way and at similar

periods. The result also shows that the average signal strength in the study area was higher in dry season compared to the signal in rainy season, given that the average RSRP value in dry season and rainy season are -107.9 dBm and -110.3 dBm respectively.

The Correlation analysis between the Reference signal received power (RSRP) and the ping or round-trip delay were carried out. This was done to study the relationship between the RSRP and the ping of the signal. From the analysis of the correlation, it was observed that the coefficients of the correlation between RSRP and ping is -0.225 (-22.5%) in dry season, and -0.109 (-10.9%) in rainy season. This shows that in both dry and rainy seasons, the signal strength and the ping have inverse relationship. In other words, as the ping or round-trip delay of the signal increases, the signal strength decreases, and as the ping reduces, the strength of the 5G network signal increases. This is in conformity with the work by [10] stating that "RSRP is sensitive to the time of ping, that long time of ping will reduce the RSRP values" and that by [11] in which it was discovered that the strongest RSRP value will be gotten when the handover time is very short, and which is related with the ping which is the time taken by the data packet to reach the server or network cell, and then back to the 5G data packet sending device.

V. Conclusion

The research work on the seasonal variation of 5G network signal speed and Signal strength over Abuja, North-Central Nigeria was carried out using the measured data of 5G such as the download, upload, ping (latency) and the signal strength (RSRP) measured in both rainy season and dry season months of 2024 beginning from July 1 to December 31, 2024. The measurement been taken hourly in Abuja in a particular experiment site using Speed test soft and Netmonitor installed on a lamp top and Infinix android phone. The results showed that there were variations in the speed of the download and the upload of the 5G network in the study area. It also showed that their variations in the received signal strength or Reference Signal Receive Power (RSRP) in the study area in both dry and rainy season.

From the results, it can be concluded that the average 5G signal strength was higher in dry season compared to the signal strength in rainy season, given that the average RSRP value in dry season and rainy season are -107.9 dBm and -110.3 dBm respectively. It can also be concluded that the signal strength is affected by the ping experienced by the network, hence, when the ping is much, the signal strength will be weak, and vice versa. The result of this work will help the network providers to install appropriate equipment in the locations and other similar locations in order to ensure fast connectivity and seamless communications. This study will also inform the infrastructural development strategies and resource allocation.

VI. Recommendation

The study has shown that there was variation of signal strength of the 5G network across Abuja, the capital of Nigeria. The result also showed the impact of ping on the signal strength. It is recommended that the effect of some atmospheric components like rainfall, pressure, temperature on the 5G network signal in Abuja be investigated in future works.

References

- [1] A. A. El-Saleh, M. A. A. Jahdhami, A. Alhammadi, Z. A. Shamsan, I. Shayea, and W. H. Hassan, "Measurements and Analyses of 4G/5G Mobile Broadband Networks: An Overview and a Case Study," *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, pp 1 – 24, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/6205689>
- [2] F. Afroz, K. Sandrasegaran, and P. Ghoshal, "Performance Analysis of PF, M-LWDF and EXP/PF Packet Scheduling Algorithms in 3GPP LTE Downlink," *Australasian Telecommunication Networks and Applications Conference (ATNAC)*, pp. 87-92, November 2014.
- [3] P. Elechi, B. Luckyn, and M. Kum, "Investigation of global system for mobile communication signal coverage in faculty of Engineering, Rivers State university, Port Harcourt, Nigeria," *Journal of Network Security Computer Networks*, 7(3): pp. 27-39, 2021.
- [4] R. Okoro and P. Iwuji, "Investigation of GSM signal strength in rural communities in the South-Eastern region of Nigeria," *European Scientific Journal*, 15(15): pp. 140-152, 2019.
- [5] O.R. Abolade, A. A. Okandjeji, F. Onaifo, A.O. Oyedeji, P.O. Alao, and A.A. Okubanjo, "A performance evaluation of 4G mobile network," *Journal of the Nigerian Association of Mathematical Physics*, 61(2021), pp. 41-46, 2021.
- [6] K.S. Bablu, J. Heena, P. Aswathy, and S. Komal, "Comparative analysis of quality of signal of different service providers," *Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 6(4), pp. 5629-5633, 2017.

- [7] A.L. Imoize, S.O. Tofade, G.U. Ughegbe, F.I. Anyasi, and J. Isabona, "Updating analysis of key performance indicators of 4G LTE network with the prediction of missing values of critical network parameters based on experimental data from a dense urban environment," *Data in Brief*, 42, pp. 108-240, 2022.
- [8] A. L. Sheu, K. O. Suleman, Q. A. Adeniji, and I. A. Azeez, "Investigation of Radio Frequency Signal Propagation of Wireless Services in Oyo, Oyo State, South Western Nigeria," *Iraqi Journal of Physics*, 22(4), pp 1-9 , 2022.
- [9] O. O. Yekeen, and A. N. Adefela, "3G, 4G, 5G Cell Tower and Their Effects On Human Health: Case Study Of The Brain," *International Journal of Engineering Applied Sciences and Technology*, 5, pp 20-24, 2020.
- [10]. Nokia, "5G Network Planning and Optimisation: RSRP and Ping Time Consideration", 2020. Available at <https://www.nokia/networks/mobile-networks/network-planning-and-optimization/>
- [11] S. Alraih, R. Nordin, I. Shayea, N. F. Abdullah, A. Abu-Samah, and A. Alhammadi, "Effectiveness of Handover Control Parameters on Handover Performance in 5G and beyond Mobile Networks. *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*," Volume 10, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/2266282>. Pp 1 - 18, 2022.
- [12] A. Abdullahi, Y. Yahuza, U.S. Amodu, O. J. Imhanfidon, E. A. Ogobor, O. S. Abimaje, J. Adejoh, R. C. Obasi, "A Study Of The Daily Weather Variation Of Abuja, North central Nigeria, A case study of the month of April," *International Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, 6(8), 7pp 6-79, 2019.